

Cyclic voltammetric and spectral studies of some complexes in copper(II)-diethyldithiocarbamate-2-methylimidazole mixed ligand systems

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Abstract : The electrochemical and spectral properties of copper(II) complexes in Cu^{II}-diethyldithiocarbamate-2-methylimidazole mixed ligand systems in different molar ratios (1 : 1 : 2, 1 : 1 : 100, 1 : 2 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 100) in acetone medium containing 0.2 M sodium perchlorate as a supporting electrolyte have been studied by using cyclic voltammetry (CV). UV-Visible absorption spectra of the above Cu^{II} : Et₂dtc⁻ : 2-MeIm systems were also recorded in acetone. On the basis of CV results, it has been concluded that two complex species are present in equilibrium in solution in Cu^{II} : Et₂dtc : 2-MeIm mixed-ligand systems in 1 : 1 : 2, 1 : 2 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 100 molar ratios and only one mixed-ligand complex species is present in 1 : 1 : 100 molar ratio.

Keywords : Cyclic voltammetry, diethyldithiocarbamate, 2-methylimidazole, Cu^{II}-mixed-ligand complexes.

Introduction

The benzimidazole ring, particularly as its 5,6-dimethyl derivative, function as ligands toward transition metal ions in a variety of biologically important molecules including iron-heme systems, vitamin B₁₂ and its derivatives and several metalloproteins¹.

Dithiocarbamates are a class of metal-chelating compounds that have previously been used in the treatment of bacterial and fungal infection and in the treatment of AIDS^{2,3}. Many biological active heterocyclic compounds containing the dithiocarbamate and/or benzimidazole moieties as well as their transition metal complexes were reported⁴⁻⁶.

As a result many fungicides, bactericides, insecticides, acaricides, nematocides and other pharmaceuticals as well as agricultural compositions were found to contain one or more of these bioactive groups. The synthesis and antifungal activity of some transition metal complexes with benzimidazole dithiocarbamate ligand have been reported⁷. Diethyldithiocarbamate complexes show various activities against the proteasome in the breast cancer cells⁸.

Dithiocarbamate ligands have stabilizing ability towards copper ions and their copper(II) complexes undergo re-

versible oxidation (Cu^{2+/3+}) and reduction (Cu^{2+/+}) processes to their monocation and monoanion, respectively⁹. Srivastava *et al.* have also reported¹⁰ the cyclic voltammetric behaviours of the binary and mixed-ligand copper(II) complexes with diethyldithiocarbamate and diimines.

In the present paper, the electrochemical and spectral (UV-Visible) behaviours of Cu^{II} complexes formed in Cu^{II}-diethyldithiocarbamate-2-MeIm mixed-ligand systems in 1 : 1 : 2, 1 : 2 : 2, 1 : 1 : 100 and 1 : 2 : 100 molar ratios have been reported. The structures of the ligands taken in the present investigation are shown below :

Diethyldithiocarbamate
(Et₂dtc⁻)

2-Methylimidazole
(2-MeIm)

Experimental

Copper perchlorate hexahydrate (Cu(ClO₄)₂·6H₂O), sodium diethyldithiocarbamate and 2-methylimidazole were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemicals Private

Ltd. and A.R. grade acetone was procured from E. Merck India Ltd. and were used as such. The CV measurements were performed on BAS Electrochemical System Model EPSILON. The auxiliary electrode was a platinum wire and reference electrode was Ag/AgCl in saturated KCl ($E^0 = +199$ mV vs NHE). Purging and blanketing of nitrogen (99.99% pure) was done for analyte solution placed in the electrochemical cell of 15 mL capacity for 20 min. Room temperature electronic absorption spectra of complexes in different molar ratios in acetone were measured in the range 1000–250 nm with a Perkin-Elmer UV-Visible spectrophotometer Model Lambda 35 available in our laboratory. 1 mM solution of $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in acetone was used in the mixed-ligand complexes. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in acetone containing 0.2 M NaClO_4 as a supporting electrolyte at a platinum working electrode at 25 ± 0.5 °C.

Results and discussion

Electrochemical behaviors of binary copper(II)-diethyldithiocarbamate complexes formed in 1 : 1 (green) and 1 : 2 (brown) molar ratios in acetone solution have been earlier reported¹⁰. It should be mentioned that $\text{Et}_2\text{-dtc}$ ligand in acetone is irreversibly oxidized to disulphide with peak potential +63 to +107 mV vs Ag/AgCl in scan rate range 25–1000 mV s^{-1} . Electrochemical behavior of binary copper(II)-2-MeIm complexes formed in 1 : 2 and 1 : 100 molar ratios have also been studied for comparison (a negative scan displayed a reversible redox couple $\text{Cu}^{2+/+}$ (c_1/a_1) with $E^{0'} = +127$ mV, $E_{\text{pc}_1} = 64$ mV, $E_{\text{pa}_1} = 190$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 126$ mV at scan rate 25 mV s^{-1} for $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-2-MeIm}$ 1 : 100 molar ratio). It should be noted that 2-methylimidazole and its copper complexes do not show any oxidation peak in the potential range studied.

Electrochemical behaviours of Cu^{II} complex species in mixed ligand $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Et}_2\text{dtc-2-MeIm}$ systems :

The electrochemical behaviours of complex species formed in mixed ligand $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Et}_2\text{dtc-2-MeIm}$ systems in 1 : 1 : 2, 1 : 2 : 2, 1 : 1 : 100 and 1 : 2 : 100 molar ratios have been studied in acetone/0.2 M NaClO_4 . The CV data are given in Tables 1 and 2 and CVs are shown in Fig. 1(a,b,c,d), respectively.

$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Et}_2\text{dtc-2-MeIm}$ 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 2 mixed-ligand systems :

In the case of $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Et}_2\text{dtc-2-MeIm}$ 1 : 1 : 2 system, a positive scan in the potential range +50 to 1100 mV displayed a reversible redox couple $\text{Cu}^{2+/3+}$ (a_1/c_1) with $E^{0'} = +488$ mV ($E_{\text{pa}_1} = 516$ mV, $E_{\text{pc}_1} = 460$ mV; $\Delta E_p = 56$ mV and $I_{\text{pc}_1}/I_{\text{pa}_1} = 1.0$) and a second irreversible anodic peak a_2 at more positive potential, $E_{\text{pa}_2} = +830$ mV at scan rate 100 mV s^{-1} (Table 1 and Fig. 1a). On the basis of CV results it may therefore be concluded that there are two complex species $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})(2\text{-MeIm})_2\text{S}_2]^+$ **1** (green coloured) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{dtc})(2\text{-MeIm})_4]^+$ **2** present in solution, where S is the solvent molecule coordinated through O-atom. Complex **1** involves Cu^{II} bonded through two S atoms of Et_2dtc^- ligand, 2 N atoms of 2-MeIm and 2O atoms of solvent molecules and complex species **2** involves a tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry

Table 1. CV data for complex species formed in $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} : \text{Et}_2\text{dtc} : 2\text{-MeIm} : 1 : 1 : 2$ and $1 : 2 : 2$ molar ratios in acetone/0.2 M NaClO_4 medium

Scan rate (mV s^{-1})	E_{pa_1} (mV)	E_{pc_1} (mV)	$E^{0'}$ (mV)	ΔE_{p_1} (mV)	$I_{\text{pc}_1}/I_{\text{pa}_1}$	E_{pa_2} (mV)	I_{pa_2}
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} : \text{Et}_2\text{dtc} : 2\text{-MeIm}$ (1 : 1 : 2)							
25	512	464	488	48	0.8	830	2.2
50	514	464	489	50	0.8	830	3.3
100	516	462	489	54	1.0	830	4.5
200	516	460	488	56	1.0	836	6.7
300	518	460	489	58	1.1	839	8.2
400	518	456	487	62	1.2	842	9.6
500	518	456	487	62	1.2	849	10.5
600	520	456	488	64	1.2	851	11.6
800	520	454	487	66	1.2	854	13.0
1000	520	454	487	66	1.4	858	14.5
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} : \text{Et}_2\text{dtc} : 2\text{-MeIm}$ (1 : 2 : 2)							
25	518	464	491	54	0.5	830	1.5
50	520	464	492	56	0.5	830	2.0
100	522	462	492	60	0.5	830	2.5
200	524	462	493	62	0.5	830	3.5
300	524	460	492	64	0.6	830	4.3
400	524	458	491	66	0.6	834	5.0
500	526	456	491	70	0.6	838	5.5
600	528	456	492	72	0.6	845	6.0
800	528	448	488	80	0.6	850	6.8
1000	532	446	489	86	0.6	860	7.5

Table 2. CV data for complex species formed in Cu^{II} : Et₂dtc : 2-MeIm : 1 : 1 : 100 and 1 : 2 : 100 molar ratios in acetone/ 0.2 M NaClO₄ medium

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{pa1} (mV)	I _{pa1}	E _{pa2} (mV)	I _{pa2}
Cu ^{II} : Et ₂ dtc : 2-MeIm (1 : 1 : 100)				
25	-	-	730	8.8
50	-	-	740	11.9
100	-	-	754	12.7
200	-	-	760	18.0
300	-	-	762	22.5
400	-	-	764	27.0
500	-	-	766	29.0
600	-	-	767	32.0
800	-	-	767	38.4
1000	-	-	770	42.5
Cu ^{II} : Et ₂ dtc : 2-MeIm (1 : 2 : 100)				
25	390	4.0	745	8.9
50	391	4.9	750	11.8
100	405	6.0	754	12.7
200	410	6.3	760	18.0
300	416	7.0	762	22.5
400	419	8.4	764	27.0
500	428	9.2	766	29.0
600	429	10.0	767	32.0
800	430	11.8	767	38.4
1000	435	12.8	770	42.5

(S₂N₄) about Cu^{II}.

The first oxidation couple Cu^{2+/3+} (a₁/c₁) may be ascribed to the oxidation of binary Cu^{II}-Et₂dtc complex, **1**. The peak current ratio (I_{pc1}/I_{pa1}) is larger than unity indicates that the oxidized complex species is adsorbed on the surface of the electrode. The second irreversible oxidation peak (a₂) is assigned to oxidation process Cu^{2+/3+} of mixed-ligand complex species **2**. It should be noted that the plot of I_{pa2} vs v^{1/2} gives a straight line passing through origin (Fig. 2), showing that the redox process Cu^{2+/3+} corresponding to mixed ligand complex, **2** is diffusion-controlled¹¹.

The CV data for complex species in 1 : 2 : 2 mixed ligand system is given in Table 1 and CV is shown in Fig. 1b at scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹. In the case of 1 : 2 : 2 mixed ligand system, a positive scan showed a redox couple a₁/c₁ (Cu^{2+/3+}) with E⁰ = +492 mV (E_{pa1} = 522 mV and E_{pc1} = 462 mV, ΔE_p = 60 mV) at 100 mV s⁻¹ due to mixed-ligand complex, [Cu(Et₂dtc)₂(2-MeIm)₂], **3** and the second irreversible anodic peak a₂ at E_{pa2} = 830 mV due to oxidation of mixed-ligand complex species [Cu(Et₂dtc)(2-MeIm)₄]⁺, **2**. It may therefore be concluded that in 1 : 2 : 2 mixed ligand system, both mixed ligand complex species **3** and **2** are present in equilibrium in solution.

Cu^{II}-Et₂dtc-2-MeIm 1 : 1 : 100 and 1 : 2 : 100 mixed-ligand systems :

In case of 1 : 1 : 100 system a positive scans exhibited only one irreversible anodic peak, a₂ at 754 mV (Table 2, Fig. 1c), indicating that only one mixed-ligand complex species [Cu(Et₂dtc)(2-MeIm)₄]⁺ **2** exists in solution.

For 1 : 2 : 100 mixed ligand system a positive scan exhibited two irreversible oxidation peaks E_{pa1} = 405 mV, E_{pa2} = 754 mV at scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹, indicating that there are two mixed-ligand complex species [Cu(Et₂dtc)(2-MeIm)₄]⁺ **2** and [Cu(Et₂dtc)₂(2-MeIm)₂]⁻ **4** present in this system (Table 2 and Fig. 1d).

Electronic spectra :

UV-Visible spectra of mixed ligand system (Cu^{II}-Et₂dtc-2-MeIm) in acetone solution in 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 : 100 molar ratios show a weak broad d-d band at 560 and 641 nm, respectively (Table 3 and Fig. 3), indicating distorted octahedral coordination geometry of the complex species around the metal centre. However, in the case of 1 : 2 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 100 molar ratios, the d-d transition bands

Fig. 1. CVs of Cu^{II} complex species in (a) 1 : 1 : 2; (b) 1 : 2 : 2; (c) 1 : 1 : 100 and (d) 1 : 2 : 100 molar ratios for $\text{Cu-Et}_2\text{dte-2-MeIm}$ systems at 100 mV s^{-1} in acetone solution containing 0.2 M NaClO_4 .

Fig. 2(a). Plots of I_{pa_2} vs $v^{1/2}$ for complex 2 in 1 : 1 : 2 (x) and 1 : 2 : 2 (y) molar ratios.

Fig. 2(b). Plots of I_{pa_2} vs $v^{1/2}$ for complex 2 in 1 : 1 : 100 and 1 : 2 : 100 molar ratios.

appeared at 605 and 607 nm. Moreover, the electronic spectra of 1 : 1 : 2, 1 : 1 : 100, 1 : 2 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 100 : $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-Et}_2\text{dte-2-MeIm}$ systems also exhibited sharp bands at 383, 382, 432 and 431 nm, respectively and is supposed to be due to ligand to metal charge transfer transitions¹² : $\text{S}(\text{Et}_2\text{dte}^-) \rightarrow \sigma^*(d_{x^2-y^2})$ of Cu^{II} supporting about

distorted octahedral geometry in all these systems. It should be noted that when the concentration of Et_2dte^- increases in the solution the band shifts from 383 nm to 432 nm (Table 3). Similar observations have earlier been made¹² in the case of $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{dte})(2,2'\text{-bipy})]^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{dte})_2$.

Table 3. Electronic absorption spectral data for mixed-ligand Cu^{II} complex species formed in different molar ratios in acetone medium

Compd.	System	Molar ratio	Colour	λ_{\max} (nm)	ϵ (L mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	Band assignments
1	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dtc : 2-MeImH	1 : 1 : 2	Green	560	310	d-d
				383	4400	CT
2	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dtc : 2-MeImH	1 : 1 : 100	Green	641	260	d-d
				382	4800	CT
3	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dtc : 2-MeIm	1 : 2 : 2	Brown	605	740	d-d
				432	10300	CT
4	Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ : Et ₂ dtc : 2-MeImH	1 : 2 : 100	Brown	607	720	d-d
				431	10200	CT

Fig. 3. Electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complex species in (a) 1 : 1 : 2 molar ratio and (b) 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratio for Cu-Et₂dtc-2-MeIm systems in acetone solution.

Conclusion

The electrochemical behaviour of mixed-ligand complex species shows that two species are present in 1 : 1 : 2 system. The green coloured mixed ligand complexes [Cu(Et₂dtc)(2-MeIm)₂S₂]⁺, **1** and [Cu(Et₂dtc)(2-MeIm)₄]⁺, **2** are present, while in 1 : 1 : 100 system only complex **2**

is present. Further, in 1 : 2 : 2, system two different complex species [Cu(Et₂dtc)₂(2-MeIm)₂], **3** and [Cu(Et₂dtc)(2-MeIm)₄]⁺, **2** are formed and in 1 : 2 : 100 system two complex species [Cu(Et₂dtc)₂(2-MeIm)₂]⁻, **4** and [Cu(Et₂dtc)(2-MeIm)₄]⁺, **2** are present. It is observed that as the concentration of 2-MeIm increases the oxida-

tion peak potentials for the mixed ligand complex species **2** becomes less positive and the concentration of the complex increases.

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